

AUDIENCE AWARENESS OF CIRDDOC AND CENGOS BROADCAST MEDIA CAMPAIGN AGAINST DOMESTIC VIOLENCE TARGETING WOMEN IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

Ozioko, Obioma Rachael

Enugu State University of Science and Technology.

Andrew C. Apeh

Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Sunny E. Udeze

Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Abstract

This study investigated the audience awareness of domestic violence against women in Enugu metropolis; a study of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns. The study adopted the descriptive research survey design. The primary instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The study discovered that the people living in the city of Enugu demonstrated low degree of awareness regarding the campaign against domestic abuse targeting women. The use of conventional media by these organizations has little impacts in raising awareness and the fear of being discriminated against was identified as the most significant factor that hindered open discussion by the victims and the study recommended implementing policies that will adequately protect victims that are courageous to testify.

Keywords: Audience awareness; CIRDDOC and CENGOS; Broadcast Media; Campaign; Women

Introduction

Domestic violence is an issue affecting individuals and communities worldwide, cutting across socio-economic, cultural, and geographic boundaries (Ikriko, 2024). In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the need to address domestic violence, particularly against women, and to implement adequate preventive measures (Kaur ,2018, Uthman et al., 2019)). With its worldwide reach and influence, the media has become a powerful tool for advocacy and awareness campaigns (Busari, 2020). The intersection of domestic violence and the media have given rise to various initiatives aimed at raising awareness, providing support, and fostering community engagement to bring the issue to an end (Busari,2020). There are various initiatives towards domestic violence awareness and two of such initiatives were discussed in this study.

Civil Resource Development And Documentation Centre (CIRDDOC) Nigeria is an independent, non-governmental and not-for-profit organization committed to the protection and promotion of human rights, gender equity and access to justice and the strengthening of civil society; Coalition Of Eastern Non-Governmental Organizations (CENGOS) is a network of over 100 civil society organizations in nine states of the old Eastern region; and Amplify Change was a campaign launched by these organizations to break the silence on Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) (Uzondu,2021).

Globally, domestic violence remains a significant public health concern, impacting the lives of millions of women. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), an estimated 1 in 3 women worldwide has experienced physical or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence in their lifetime (WHO,2020). The adverse effects of domestic violence on women's physical and mental well-being, as well as its broader societal implications, underscore the urgency of comprehensive strategies to address and prevent such violence (Lanchimba,2023).

In the Nigerian context, domestic violence is a deeply rooted social issue with profound implications for women's rights and public health (Busari,2020). The National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) in Nigeria revealed that 28% of women aged 15-49 have experienced physical violence, while 7% have experienced sexual violence (NPC & ICF, 2019). Enugu, as one of the prominent states in Nigeria, is not free of the prevalence of domestic violence.

Statement of the problem

South-East Nigeria has a disproportionate burden of female circumcision. Female Genital Mutilation (FGM), Female Genital Cutting (FGC) or Female Circumcision, is a fundamental violation of womanhood accounting for about 55% of the female rights abuse all over the world. FGM is an unhealthy traditional practice inflicted on girls and women worldwide. It is widely recognized as a violation of human rights which is deeply rooted in cultural beliefs and perceptions over decades, and which is stoutly resisting extinction. Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C) encompasses all illegal surgical procedures involving partial or total removal of the external female genitalia for cultural or other non-therapeutic reasons. The UNICEF (2018) reported that the national FGM/C prevalence among women age 15-49 is 20%. However, the prevalence of FGM is highest in the South East (35%) and South West (30%) and lowest in the North East (6%). UNICEF (2016) further revealed that in the South East, Enugu occupies 25.3%. All these and many other forms of domestic violence targeting women in Enugu metropolis prompted the researcher to ask: "What is the level of audience awareness of CIRDDON and CENGOS broadcast media campaign against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu state?"

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this work is to establish the audience awareness of CIRDDON and CENGOS broadcast media campaign against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu state.

The specific objectives are further broken down into the following;

1. To assess the level of awareness in Enugu state metropolis regarding CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu metropolis.
2. To explore the factors influencing the engagement with CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu metropolis

Research Questions

This research seeks to answer the following questions;

1. To what extent are residents of Enugu metropolis aware of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women?
2. What are the factors influencing their engagement with CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu state?

Significance of the Study

The primary significance of this study is contributing to both academic understanding and practical interventions in addressing the issue of domestic violence against women within Enugu metropolis. By investigating the audience awareness of broadcast media campaigns, the research aims to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of media advocacy in shaping awareness related to domestic violence. The findings are expected to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the

intersection of broadcast media and public awareness, particularly in the context of eliminating domestic violence. The study's outcome will be a foundational resource for policymakers, advocacy groups, and broadcast media strategists involved in designing and implementing campaigns against domestic violence. Furthermore, the research will empower community leaders, NGOs, and other stakeholders with evidence-based insights to tailor support services and educational programs for those affected by domestic violence. This study aspires to bridge the gap between academic inquiry and practical application, offering actionable findings that can enhance broadcast media campaigns and public awareness and, ultimately, prevent domestic violence against women in Enugu metropolis.

Scope of the Study

Unit scope: This study focused on the audience awareness of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaign.

Content scope: The content of this study centered on CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaign themed '**Amplify Change**', **other** domestic violence issues and women.

Geographical scope: This scope encompasses three local government areas in Enugu metropolis. They are Enugu North, Enugu South and Enugu East.

Unit of Analysis: The unit that was studied here includes: audience awareness and factors or challenges preventing audience engaging to the campaign

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Framework

Spiral of Silence Theory

The spiral of silence was propounded by Noelle-Neuman (1984); it states that because of people's fear of isolation or separation from those around them, they tend to keep their attitudes to themselves when they think they are in the minority. The media, because of a variety of factors, tend to present one (or at most two) sides of an issue to the exclusion of others, which further encourages those people to keep quiet and may register that opposing view (Baran & Davies, 2019). If media reports ignore, marginalize, or trivialize various viewpoints about agenda items, people will feel reluctant about them. Neuman is concerned with the long-term consequences of these perceptions.

Relating this to this study, there is a spiral of silence on violence against women generally. As the media is currently the primary source of information, public perceptions about domestic violence among women are biased, as there are a lack of convincing details and enough views, especially in newspapers, social groups, and social media platforms. Women have a fear of shame in society, isolation from friends and family, stigma of being a woman in a failed marriage, and as a result, deliberately do not discuss/report any act of violence against them by their husbands but rather keep quiet.

In a 2020 campaign organized by CIRDDOC in partnership with CENGOS to sensitize the people in Eastern Nigeria states on why they should leave abusive marriages, eliminate FGM and also to fight against it, while seeking governmental support to put a ban on such barbaric act, the women who as at then felt safe, were found to be back home to their spouses, apologizing profusely to them and promising to submit and remain in their roles as women who are to make the home. According to the campaign spokesperson, Uzoamaka Aguoma, those women have been brainwashed and forced by society to believe that leaving a marriage that is not working for you will end up being detrimental to you. Out of the 300 women that were gathered for the campaign, the NGO in their monthly check ins said that more than half of them went back to their abusive spouses.

This goes to agree with this theory, that not only does the media post biased stories, sometimes, these women feel afraid and do not know any other life besides the one lived with their husbands and as such, they return to what is familiar and the cycle goes on.

Empirical Review

The mass media campaign on gender-based violence in Nigeria has been viewed as an obligation to educate and motivate communities by disseminating accurate information, allowing people to identify the underlying issues, and providing solutions to human rights abuses. An effective campaign influences behavior through the audience's direct exposure to persuasive messages.

A study on Domestic Violence against Women in the Nigerian Rural Context by Adegok et al. (2018) using open-ended questionnaire, observed that advocacy organizations should use more realistic and practical communication channels specific to each rural location. For example, using indigenous languages to create songs, plays, and sayings to express the consequences of domestic violence against women in their communities may be a better approach.

According to Anene (2019), in *Countering Violence Against Women by Encouraging Disclosure: A Mass Media Experiment in Rural Uganda*, the results of interviews performed a few months after the initiative indicated dismissive attitudes toward justifying violence against Women but a considerable rise in eagerness to disclose to authorities, particularly among women, and a decrease in the proportion of women that suffered abuse.

A study on “Perception of the Influence of Television Broadcasts in the Campaign Against Discrimination and Violence Among Women” by Bangert-Drowns et al., (2021) which adopted a quantitative research method, found that the level of awareness of the campaign against discrimination and violence among women based on their exposure to television broadcast is minimal at 50% and that television broadcasts in the campaign against discrimination and violence against women were perceived to be unsatisfactory at 46.1%. In essence, the finding indicated that exposure to television broadcasts does not significantly influence women’s participation in the campaign against discrimination and violence among them at 44%.

Social media could be utilized to eradicate violence and sexual harassment in Nigeria (Eboh et al., 2017). The study found that poverty is one of the leading issues that is currently increasing the abuse against the female gender in Nigeria. Social media was affirmed as one of the tools that have been helping women speak for their rights, and it also serves as a mechanism for proper enlightenment on protecting themselves.

In a study on the use of mass media campaigns to improve health behavior by Wakefield et al. (2015) discovered that mass media campaigns can induce positive outcomes or avoid negative changes in health-related behaviors across broad populations. What contributed to these outcomes, according to the authors, is the simultaneous provision and accessibility of essential services and products, the existence of community-based programs, and policies that hold up behavior change.

In contrast, a study by Fakunmoju and Rasool (2018), found that the media, through the campaign messages, are not over-protecting the women and do not make the women not to be submissive. They observed in their study on “exposure to violence and beliefs about violence against women in Nigeria and South Africa” that most of the respondents believe that: “physical violence against women is justified as there are times a woman deserves to be beaten”; women are trained to tolerate abusive relationships to keep their marriages/relationships; and men have the right to punish the spouse if she does something wrong.

A study on “Perception of the Influence of Television Broadcast’s in the Campaign Against Discrimination and Violence Among Women” by Orji et al. (2021) found that the level of awareness of the campaign against discrimination and violence among women based on their exposure to

television broadcast is minimal at 50% and that television broadcasts in the campaign against discrimination and violence against women were perceived to be unsatisfactory at 46.1%. In essence, the finding indicated that exposure to television broadcasts do not significantly influence women's participation in the campaign against discrimination and violence among them at 44%.

A study on Domestic Violence against Women in the Nigerian Rural Context by Igbolekwu et al. (2021), observed that advocacy organizations should use more realistic and effective communication channels specific to each rural location, such as the use of indigenous languages to create songs, plays, and proverbs to express the consequences of domestic violence against women in their communities may be a better approach.

Hall (2022) in his study "Spousal violence in Southwest Nigeria: Prevalence and correlates." explores the prevalence and correlates of spousal violence in Southwest Nigeria, highlighting the significant social and cultural factors that contribute to domestic violence in this region and how to curtail it.

Ibekwe (2017). In his study "Domestic Violence against Women in Nigeria: Experiences of Women in Abuja." provides an in-depth look at the experiences of women in Abuja, Nigeria, who have faced domestic violence, offering personal narratives and statistical analysis to illustrate the issue.

Ifemeje et al., (2022) in their studies "Factors influencing gender-based violence among men and women in selected states in Nigeria." investigates the various gender factors that influence gender-based violence in Nigeria, providing insights into the socio-economic and cultural drivers of domestic violence.

Okemgbo, et al (2022). In their study "Prevalence, patterns and correlates of domestic violence in selected Igbo communities of Imo State, Nigeria."* focused on Igbo communities in Imo State, their study examined the prevalence, patterns, and correlates of domestic violence, offering a regional perspective on the issue.

Eze-Anaba (2016). In his study "Domestic violence and legal reforms in Nigeria: Prospects and challenges." discusses the legal aspects of domestic violence in Nigeria, analyzing the effectiveness of existing laws and the challenges faced in implementing legal reforms to protect women. Paramio and Campos(2020) In their study "The impact of domestic violence on women's health in Rivers State, Nigeria." highlights the health impacts of domestic violence on women in Rivers State, Nigeria, emphasizing the physical and psychological consequences and the need for improved health care responses.

Amnesty International. (2015). In their report "Nigeria: Unheard Voices: Violence Against Women in the Family." sheds light on the often-overlooked issue of family violence against women in Nigeria, emphasizing the need for legal reforms and better enforcement of existing laws

2.4 Gap in Literature

This chapter discussed the position of other studies on domestic violence and audience awareness of the concept. It looked at their views, arguments, sentiments, and opinions relevant to this study. In summary, the chapter argued that domestic violence is one of the most prevalent issues that women suffer. This violence comes from various reasons, most of them being psychological. It also showed that most men exert violence on women to satisfy their egos and feel powerful. The study also looked at reasons why women find it hard to leave their abusers and how the majority of them end up blaming themselves. However, all studies reviewed in the work did not give focus on the effect of CIRDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns and how it has influenced audience awareness with regard to domestic violence in Enugu metropolis. This work will therefore, fill the gaps that the older studies failed to cover.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a descriptive survey research design was used. Descriptive surveys focus on people's characteristics, attitudes, and behaviors. According to Nworgu (2015), it investigates a selected group to determine the incidence and distribution of factors. This method is practical and cost-effective, allowing efficient data collection through questionnaires.

Area of study

This study was carried out in the three local government areas in Enugu state. They are Enugu North, Enugu South and Enugu East.

Sources of Data

A well-structured questionnaire was used to generate data from residents of Enugu metropolis through a face-to-face method.

Population of the Study

This study collected data from residents of Enugu Metropolis. Enugu metropolis comprises of Enugu East, 397, 700, Enugu North, 347,500 and Enugu South 284,200. Bringing the population to 1, 029,400 (City Population,2021).

Determination of sample size

A sample size of 385 was drawn from the population using Australian online calculator. The researcher used an error margin of 5%. A click on the calculate button results in a sample size of 385. Hence, the answer above.

The image shows a screenshot of a web-based calculator titled "Determine Sample Size". The interface is green and white. It contains several input fields and radio buttons. The "Confidence Level" is set to 95%. The "Population Size" is 1029400. The "Proportion" is 0.5. The "Confidence Interval" is 0.05000, with "Upper" at 0.55000 and "Lower" at 0.45000. The "Standard Error" is 0.02551. The "Relative Standard Error" is 5.10. The "Sample Size" is 385. There are "Calculate" and "Clear" buttons at the bottom.

Field	Value
Confidence Level	95%
Population Size	1029400
Proportion	0.5
Confidence Interval	0.05000
Upper	0.55000
Lower	0.45000
Standard Error	0.02551
Relative Standard Error	5.10
Sample Size	385

Sampling Technique

To achieve the desired results and findings in this study, the researcher adopted the Multistage Sampling technique to determine the process of administering the required copies of the questionnaire. Multistage Sampling refers to sampling plans where the sampling is carried out in stages using smaller and smaller sampling units at each stage. The final stage of sampling involves choosing a random sample of people in the clusters selected at the penultimate stage. For the purpose

of the study, the sample population was Enugu metropolis. The breakdown of the stages are as follows;

STAGES

Stage 1	Enugu metropolis
Stage 2	Cluster sampling was used to select three neighborhoods each from the three Local Government Areas. Abakpa, New Haven and Trans Ekulu from Enugu East, Independence Layout, Obiagu and GRA from Enugu North, Achara Layout, Uwani and Awkunanaw from Enugu South. The copies of questionnaire were shared in each Local Government Area in line with the number.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered all the copies of the structured questionnaire to the respondents in Enugu metropolis. The questionnaires were given to the selected sample for the study who are adults and can make informed decisions. In the course of this study, the researcher employed the primary method of data collection. Since the study was an empirical one, the data for this exercise were obtained from information gathered from the items on the questionnaire, distributed and collected by the researcher. The questionnaire was self-administered.

Validity of the Research Instrument

To ensure the validity of the research instruments used in this study, several steps were taken. Firstly, the questionnaire was carefully structured to accurately measure the intended concepts, with each question designed to effectively capture the relevant variables under investigation. Additionally, the questionnaire was reviewed by two lecturers in Mass Communication and one in Psychology to assess its content validity and ensure it adequately addresses the research objectives. Feedback from these experts were used to refine the questionnaire before it was administered to the full sample.

Reliability of the instrument

A test-retest method was employed to assess the reliability of the instrument. The researcher conducted a pilot study with a two-week interval using the questionnaire, which showed consistent results. This test-retest approach ensured that the questions provided reliable data before the full administration of the survey.

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher used tables and simple percentages for the purpose of presenting and analyzing the research questions for this study. This was to make simplicity of data presentation and analysis and its comprehension on the part of readers of this work.

Data Presentation

Data were presented using tables

Data Analysis

Data generated were analyzed using simple percentage

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Age Group	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
18-25	150	40.5	40.5
26-35	120	32.4	32.4
36-45	60	16.2	16.2
46-55	25	6.8	6.8
56+	15	4.1	4.1
Total	370	100.0	100.0

The age distribution in Table 1 indicates that 150 respondents, representing 40.5%, are between the ages of 18-25. 120 respondents, or 32.4%, are within the ages of 26-35. 60 respondents, accounting for 16.2%, are between 36-45 years old. 25 respondents, making up 6.8%, are aged 46-55, and 15 respondents, representing 4.1%, are 56 years and above. This implies that the majority of respondents are young adults, predominantly within the ages of 18-35, reflecting a significant portion of the population likely to engage with and be impacted by campaigns against domestic violence.

Table 2: Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent(%)
Single	130	35.1	35.1
Married	200	54.1	54.1
Divorced	20	5.4	5.4
Other	20	5.4	5.4
Total	370	100.0%	100.0%

Table 2 shows that 130 respondents, or 35.1%, are single. 200 respondents, representing 54.1%, are married. 20 respondents, accounting for 5.4%, are divorced, and another 20 respondents, also 5.4%, fall into the 'Other' category. This distribution suggests that a significant portion of the respondents are married, which may influence their perception and awareness of domestic violence campaigns.

Table 3: Education Level of Respondents

Education Level	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
FSLC	20	5.4	5.4
SSCE	100	27.0	27.0
NCE/OND	120	32.4	32.4

Education Level	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
HND/B.Sc	90	24.3	24.3
Master's	30	8.1	8.1
Ph.D	10	2.7	2.7
Total	370	100.0%	100.0%

Table 4: Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
Civil Servant	50	32.4	32.4
Private Worker	70	18.9	18.9
Business/Trader	80	21.6	21.6
Student	120	13.5	13.5
Unemployed	20	5.4	5.4
Farmer	10	2.7	2.7
Other	20	5.4	5.4
Total	370	100.0%	100.0%

The analysis of psychographic data deals with analyzing data gathered from the behavior, attitude and mind set of the respondents towards the campaign.

Research Question One: To what extent are residents of Enugu metropolis aware of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women?

Table 5: HAVE YOU EVER HEARD OF CIRDDOC and CENGOS Amplify Change broadcast media campaign addressing the issue of Domestic against Women in Enugu Metropolis?

Response	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
Strongly Agree	30	8.1	8.1
Agree	90	24.3	24.3
Disagree	100	27.0	40.5
Strongly Disagree	150	40.5	27.0
Total	370	100.0	100.0

Table 5 shows that 100 respondents, representing 27.0%, strongly disagree that they have encountered CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media addressing domestic violence against women in Enugu metropolis. 150 respondents representing 40.5%, disagree with this statement. This suggests that majority of respondents are unaware of the campaign and by implication, there is a low level of awareness of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media in Enugu metropolis.

Research Question Two: What are the factors that influence the engagement of Enugu metropolis residents with CIRDDOC and CENGOS campaigns against domestic violence.

Table 6: Fear of being stigmatized, personal experiences or stories shared by survivors of domestic violence are influential in discouraging audience engagement with the campaigns on the issue

Response	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)
Strongly Agree	130	35.1	35.1
Agree	140	37.8	37.8
Disagree	85	23.0	23.0
Strongly Disagree	15	4.1	4.1
Total	370	100.0	100.0

Field Survey (2024)

Table 6 shows that 130 respondents, representing 35.1%, strongly agree that fear of being stigmatized, personal experiences or stories shared by survivors of domestic violence are factors discouraging their engagement with CIRDDOC and CENGOS campaigns on the issue. 140 respondents, or 37.8%, agree with this statement. 85 respondents, making up 23.0%, disagree, and 15 respondents, representing 4.1%, strongly disagree. This data suggests that discriminatory experiences from survivors is the most significant factor discouraging audience engagement with the campaigns.

Discussion of findings

This section discusses the findings of the study in relation to the research questions that were raised.

Research Question One: To what extent are residents of Enugu metropolis aware of CIRDDOC and CENGOS campaigns against domestic violence targeting women?

The findings reveal that a significant majority of residents in Enugu metropolis are unaware of CIRDDOC and CENGOS broadcast media campaigns against domestic violence targeting women in Enugu metropolis. According to Table 5, 40.5% of respondents indicated unawareness of these campaigns. This contradicts with the findings of Orji (2021), who emphasize that awareness campaigns are crucial in empowering individuals to seek support and assistance when facing domestic violence.

Research Question Two: What are the factors that influence the engagement of Enugu metropolis residents with CIRDDOC and CENGOS campaigns against domestic violence?

The findings revealed that the fear of being stigmatized or discriminated against was a significant factor that hindered open discussion by victims. CIRDON and CENGOS strive to include varied narratives that reflect different socio-economic, cultural, and personal backgrounds. A study by Eboh and Ijeoma (2017) highlights the importance of inclusive messaging in social campaigns, which ensures that diverse groups feel represented and heard. The accuracy of information disseminated in campaigns is crucial for maintaining public trust and engagement. Misleading or inaccurate content can have a detrimental impact, causing skepticism and disengagement. According to Uthman, Lawoko, and Moradi (2019), gender discrimination can undermine the credibility of campaigns and hinder their effectiveness. Respondents who encounter discriminatory content are likely to disengage, highlighting the need for rigorous fact-checking and truthful communication in all campaign materials. Stigma faced by those who shared by survivors of domestic violence are powerful tools for demoralizing engagement. These narratives provide real-life context and emotional resonance, making the issue more tangible and urgent for the audience but was a means of discouragement. Adegoke and Udegbe (2018) found that personal stories significantly enhance the emotional appeal of campaigns and foster a deeper connection with the cause. Respondents strongly disagree that survivor stories are influential in motivating their engagement underscore the effectiveness of using personal narratives in advocacy work.

Summary of Findings

In the course of this study, the following findings were made:

1. The study found out that the residents of Enugu metropolis exhibit a low level of awareness regarding the campaigns against domestic violence targeting women.
2. Fear of being discriminated against is the primary factor hindering the audience from engaging effectively with the campaign.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be said that residents of Enugu metropolis exhibit a low level of awareness regarding the campaigns and fear of being discriminated against was the most significant factors that impedes audience engagement and testimony.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this research, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Given the reasonable level of unawareness among residents, CIRDDOC and CENGOS should invest more on sufficient awareness and continue to expand their outreach efforts through diverse media channels. This can include leveraging traditional and digital media and increase the frequency and reach of community-based workshops, seminars, and town hall meetings to ensure even the most remote areas are informed.
2. There should be an active law protecting survivors who are willing to give testimonies from all forms of discriminations regarding domestic violence.

Contribution to knowledge

This study has contributed in providing data not only on domestic violence against women but has also amplified the voices of CIRDDOC and CENGOS as an NGOs involved in eradicating all forms of discrimination against women especially in Enugu metropolis.

Suggestions for further studies

Based on the findings, we are suggesting that further studies should focus other media channels or media preference by residents of Enugu metropolis when accessing information related to domestic violence by either the government or NGOs.

References

- Adegoke, T. G., & Udegbe, I. B. (2018). Personal stories in advocacy campaigns: Enhancing emotional appeal and engagement. *Journal of Communication and Media Studies, 10*(2), 134-150.
- Anene, C. U. (2019). Media campaigns and societal issues: Shaping public opinion and encouraging collective action. *Journal of Public Relations Research, 25*(4), 362-375.
- Bangert-Drowns, R. L., Kulik, J. A., & Kulik, C.-L. C. (2021). The importance of empowerment in awareness campaigns: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Social Issues, 60*(3), 563-583.
- Bosch, T. (2016). The role of broadcast media in shaping first opinions: Evidence from the 2012 U.S. presidential campaign. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication, 21*(6), 520-539.
- City Population (2021). City population- statistics, maps and charts <https://citypopulation.com>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2019). Community-based interventions and collective action against violence. *Educational Psychologist, 54*(2), 132-152.
- Eboh, E. C., & Ijeoma, J. N. (2017). Inclusive messaging in social campaigns: Ensuring diverse representation. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy, 37*(9/10), 555-572.
- Hall, S. (2022). Spousal violence in Southwest Nigeria: Prevalence and correlates. *Cultural Studies, 33*(1), 112-129.
- Ifemeje, S. C., & Ikpeze, N. S. (2022). Factors influencing gender-based violence among men and women in selected states in Nigeria. *Gender & Behaviour, 20*(1), 1474-1489.
- Ikriko, S. (2024). Providing information and support to vulnerable populations through media. *Journal of Communication, 65*(4), 551-572.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2023). Population of Enugu metropolis. www.nbs.org
- NPC (2019). Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. Rockville, Maryland,
- Osuala, E. C. (2001). Introduction to research methodology. African First Publishers.
- Paramio, J. L., & Campos, C. A. (2020). The impact of domestic violence on women's health in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Community Psychology, 48*(3), 617-632.
- Roediger, H. L., Putnam, A. L., & Smith, M. A. (2019). Awareness campaigns and support-seeking behavior in domestic violence victims. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied, 25*(3), 313-325.
- Ross, S. M. (2016). Media campaigns in empowering individuals and influencing social change. *Journal of Health Communication, 21*(2), 179-188.
- Uthman, O. A., Lawoko, S., & Moradi, T. (2019). Misinformation and its impact on the effectiveness of campaigns. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence, 34*(1), 153-175.
- World Health Organization. (2010). Addressing and mitigating domestic violence through sustained advocacy and education. *WHO Report on Violence and Health, 123-145*.
- World Health Organization. (2020). Violence against women prevalence estimates, 2018. Retrieved from <https://int.org>
- . United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) (2016) Children's and Women's Right in Nigeria: A Wake up call. Situation Assessment and Analysis. Harmful Traditional Practice (FGM). Abuja, NPC and UNICEF Nigeria. pp195-200 12.
- United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) (2018). Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting: A global concern. UNICEF, New York
- Uzundu, C. (2021). situation assessment and analysis of female genital mutilation/cutting in Imo and Ebonyi states report-of-a-baseline-study-on-fgm.docx.pdf (cirddoc.org)